

Organophilic Characteristics of Organic Derivatives of Bentonite, Kaolinite, Alumina and their Binary Mixtures

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Long-chain quaternary ammonium cations can replace the exchangeable cations present on certain clays, viz. montmorillonite, and the resulting clays have the important property of dispersion in a variety of organic solvents. Several workers have studied the change in the organophilic characteristics and other physical properties of organo-clay complexes^{1,2}. In the present investigation, the organophilic characteristics of organic derivatives of bentonite, kaolinite, alumina and their binary mixtures have been studied from the total intake of toluene and water as well as from the behaviour towards pairs of immiscible or partially miscible liquids.

Results and Discussion

The total intakes of water and toluene by clay-organic complexes are shown in Fig. 1. It is evident from the data (Table 1) that the bentonite complexes have higher rate of toluene intake and lower rate of water intake than kaolinite and alumina complexes. The equilibrium between the complexes and water or toluene is quickly established in the

case of kaolinite and alumina complexes. The bentonite complexes, presumably due to the presence of larger number of water-repellant groups, take up less water at a rate much more slowly than those for kaolinite and alumina complexes. The intake of toluene and water by the organic complexes of bentonite and kaolinite shows additivity with the composition. But the organic complexes of the binary mixtures of bentonite and alumina do not follow additivity (Fig. 1).

The linear relationship between the total intake of water and toluene by the organic complexes of binary mixtures of bentonite and kaolinite with their composition suggests that the component clays retain more or less their individual characteristics. But deviation from the additivity in the case of organic complexes of bentonite and alumina may be due to the changed physicochemical properties of bentonite by alumina. Davey and Low³ observed a marked effect on viscosity and water tension due to the effect of freshly precipitated hydrous aluminium oxide on Na-saturated Wyoming bentonite. The higher toluene intake than water intake by the organic derivatives of bentonite shows that the organic portions are attached to the clay surface thus rendering the clay more or less hydrophobic and organophilic in character. However, the organic derivatives of bentonite, kaolinite, alumina as well as all the complexes have retained more toluene than water. Similar observations were also made by Chakravarti and Mukherjee² for montmorillonite, illite and kaolinite complexes.

The development of organophilic character in the clay organic complexes can be studied from the behaviour of organic complexes in pairs of immiscible solvents. The observations are given in Table 2. In the pairs of immiscible solvents, in which water is a common constituent, bentonite complexes prefer organic phase whereas kaolinite and alumina complexes prefer water phase.

Experimental

Bentonite (Evans Medical Ltd., U.K.) and kaolinite (B.D.H.) (particle size $<2 \mu\text{m}$) were isolated by the usual method of dispersion and sedimentation. The fractions so collected were then treated with 6% H_2O_2 in slightly acidic media to remove traces of organic matter, if any. The free iron oxide was removed from bentonite fraction by citrate-bicarbonate-dithionite method⁴. The clays were then con-

Fig. 1. Additivity of total water (\blacktriangle , \blacksquare , \bullet) and toluene (\triangle , \square , \circ) intake of organic derivatives of clay binary mixtures: (\ast , \circ) CP derivatives of B, K, (\blacksquare , \square) CTA derivatives of B, A, and (\blacktriangle , \triangle) CTA derivatives of B, K, and their mixtures.

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TABLE 1—RATE OF WATER AND TOLUENE INTAKE BY ORGANIC DERIVATIVES OF BENTONITE, KAOLINITE, ALUMINA AND THEIR BINARY MIXTURES

Sample	Composition*	Time h	Intake of water ml g ⁻¹ sample	Intake of toluene ml g ⁻¹ sample
CTA-bentonite	-	0.25	0.08	4.40
		0.5	0.15	4.75
		1.0	0.19	4.90
		2.0	0.22	5.05
		3.0	0.25	5.15
		4.0	0.27	5.25
CTA-Kaolinite	-	0.25	1.08	1.50
		0.5	1.20	1.56
		1.0	1.26	1.58
		2.0	1.28	1.62
		3.0	1.30	1.65
		4.0	1.31	1.67
CTA-Alumina	-	0.25	1.18	1.38
		0.5	1.25	1.46
		1.0	1.28	1.48
		2.0	1.30	1.49
		3.0	1.31	1.50
		4.0	1.31	1.50
CTA-Mix. I	B : K = 2 : 1	0.25	0.62	3.41
		0.5	0.67	3.63
		1.0	0.69	3.72
		2.0	0.72	3.77
		3.0	0.73	3.81
		4.0	0.74	3.84
CTA-Mix. II	B : K = 1 : 2	0.25	0.80	2.64
		0.5	0.90	2.72
		1.0	0.95	2.75
		2.0	0.98	2.79
		3.0	0.99	2.82
		4.0	1.00	2.84
CTA-Mix. V	B : A = 2 : 1*	0.25	0.51	3.80
		0.5	0.67	3.95
		1.0	0.72	4.01
		2.0	0.77	4.12
		3.0	0.79	4.16
		4.0	0.81	4.18
CTA-Mix. VI	B : A = 1 : 2	0.25	1.02	2.70
		0.5	1.12	2.85
		1.0	1.15	2.90
		2.0	1.17	2.95
		3.0	1.19	2.98
		4.0	1.21	2.99
		5.0	1.23	3.00

B = Bentonite, K = kaolinite, A = alumina.

verted to the H-form by resin (Amberlite IR 120) treatment.

Binary mixtures of different weight ratios of bentonite

and kaolinite and bentonite and alumina were prepared by adding slowly one sol (1%) into the other at room temperature under continuous shaking. The mixtures were allowed to equilibrate with occasional shaking for more than one month. The clay-organic complexes were prepared by reacting aqueous suspensions of H-clay (1%) or their binary mixtures with aqueous solutions of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC). The clay-organic complexes were then washed free of electrolytes, dried at 30° and pulverised to 100 mesh.

TABLE 2—BEHAVIOUR OF THE CLAY-ORGANIC COMPLEXES TOWARDS PAIRS OF PARTIALLY MISCIBLE OR IMMISCIBLE SOLVENT OF WHICH WATER IS A COMMON CONSTITUENT*

Sample	Ether	Nitro-benzene	CCl ₄	Cyclo-hexane	n-Butanol
CTA-bentonite	O',I ₂	O	O',I ₂	O',W'	O',I ₁
CTA-kaolinite	W',I ₁ ,I ₂	W',I ₁	W',I ₁	W	O',I ₂ ,W'
CP-bentonite	O',I ₂	O	W',I ₁	W',O'	O',I ₂
CP-kaolinite	W',I ₂	W',I ₁	W',I ₁	W	W',I ₁
CTA-alumina	W	W	W	W	W
CP-alumina	W	W	W	W	W
CTA-Mix. V (B : A = 2 : 1)	O',I ₂ ,W'	O',W'	O',W',I ₂	O',W'	O',W'
CTA-Mix. II (B : A = 1 : 2)	W',I ₂	O',W'	W',I ₁ ,I ₂	O',W'	O',I ₁ ,I ₂

*W and O = Practically all the sample goes to the water and organic phase respectively, W' and O' = some portion of the sample goes to the water and organic liquid phase respectively, I₁ and I₂ = some portion of the sample goes to the interface towards water and to the interface towards organic liquid respectively.

The total intakes of water and toluene per g of the clay-organic complexes were determined⁵. For studying the behaviour of the clay-organic complexes towards pairs of partially miscible or immiscible solvents, of which water is a common constituent, the solid sample (0.1 g) was first shaken with water followed by adding equal volumes of the organic solvent and allowed to stand undisturbed for 24 h. The phase to which the given clay-organic complex passes was noted.

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